

Prevalence and Determinants of Alcohol Use in Benue South Senatorial District, Nigeria

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More Information

How to cite this article: Obekpa IO, Agbo PE, Amedu AM, Itodo SA. Prevalence and Determinants of Alcohol Use in Benue South Senatorial District, Nigeria. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(2):120-6.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(2).13

Keywords:

Alcohol use,
Benue south,
determinants,
prevalence.

Abstract

Introduction: Despite the huge public health problems of alcohol use, there is no community data in Benue South, Senatorial District. The aim of the study was to determine the prevalence of alcohol use and their determinants in Benue South Senatorial District.

Materials and Method: 400 participants aged 18 to 60 years, who consented, were recruited consecutively in Okpokwu, Otukpo and Ohimini Local Government Areas (LGAs). A 3-part questionnaire, including the WHO Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST) was administered to the participants.

Results: The mean age was 29.12 years \pm 10.5. The lifetime prevalence of alcohol use was 77.5% and the prevalence of current alcohol use was 47.5%. The study found no determinant of alcohol use. There was no association between alcohol use and gender ($p=0.163$), age ($p=0.043$), educational level ($p=0.934$), community control of alcohol use ($p=0.451$) and ease of obtaining alcohol ($p=0.920$).

Conclusion: Further research on alcohol use alongside routine screening and appropriate interventions in facilities is an important public health action.

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Introduction

Alcohol consumption, even in low quantities, comes with risk and harms to health, occupation, safety and general wellbeing [1,2]. Globally, harmful use of alcohol remains a public health problem with high morbidity and mortality rates [2]. Although some studies have demonstrated modest health benefits of light-moderate alcohol consumption [3,4], far more studies show that consumption of larger quantities of alcohol and for prolonged periods is associated with adverse health, social, legal and economic consequences [1,5,6]. As a result, the World Health Organization (WHO) has continued to review downwards the graded risk levels of alcohol use [1]. Available data in Nigeria

shows a preponderance of institution-based research among young persons giving a skewed perspective of the alcohol research narrative. It is important to have more community-based data of alcohol use and its associated determinants.

Alcohol Use Burden

Of the nearly 7 billion world population, roughly a third (2.3 billion people) currently drink alcohol [8]. Nearly 45% of the proportion of alcohol consumed is spirits [7]. This is followed by beer (34.3%) and wine (11.7%) [9]. Although there are wide regional variations in the consumption of alcohol, there has been an increased drinking of alcohol in almost all regions since 2000 except in the WHO European Region [7].

Between 2005 and 2016, total alcohol per capital consumption has increased in the global population of 15 years of age and above from 5.5 litres to 6.4 litres in roughly a decade (2005-2016 [9]). This increase is particular in WHO European Region, whereas in Africa, America and Eastern Mediterranean, it has remained stable. By 2025, it is projected that the total alcohol per capital consumption will increase up to 7.0 litres in the region of Americas, South-East Asia and Western Pacific with the corresponding substantial decrease in other parts of the world making no overall change in figure [7].

Prevalence of Heavy Episodic Drinking (HED) (Defined as ≥ 60 g of pure alcohol on at least one or more occasion at least once a month) has decreased from 22.6% in 2000 to 18.2% in 2016 [7]. HED remains high among drinkers in parts of Eastern Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa. HED is particularly high among men and among 20–24-year-olds [7].

Across all WHO regions of the world, there is a direct association between the economic wealth of countries and higher alcohol consumption and higher prevalence of current drinkers [7]. In most regions except in Africa and Europe, the prevalence of HED is fairly equal in low- and high-income countries. In Europe, the prevalence of HED is low in low-income countries compared to high-income countries. In Africa it is higher for low-income countries compared to high-income countries. "Although the highest levels of alcohol consumption are in Europe, Africa bears the heaviest burden of disease and injury attributed to alcohol" [7]

Moral perceptions of persons who use alcohol and other psychoactive substances vary widely across cultures and societies and at different times [8]. Epidemiological studies on use of alcohol and other psychoactive substances are fraught with underreporting, minimization and even outright denial of harmful drinking pattern in Nigeria possibly due to perceptions of low moral and religious standing of users of these substances [9]. On the other end of the continuum, are persons who freely report their drinking pattern because alcohol is not even considered a drug, but a necessary beverage for social recreation and customary rites and events [10].

In most parts of Nigeria, Beer and palm wine and other locally brewed alcoholic beverages are the most consumed alcoholic beverages [11], however, the proliferation of spirits and gin in sachets in almost every hamlet, village and city appears to have distorted this traditional pattern of beer-palm wine consumption [12]. Various figures have been reported for the prevalence of alcohol use in Nigeria. Lasebikan and Ola [13] reported a current use prevalence of alcohol to be 23.7% in a semirural community in South West Nigeria. Onodugbo et al [14] reported a prevalence of 66.7% in an urban slum in South East Nigeria. Adeloye et al [15],

reported a pooled crude prevalence of harmful use of alcohol of 34.3% in a systematic review and meta-analysis. Majority of the epidemiological data on alcohol use comes from studies on university students and young populations, because it is widely believed that alcohol use and its associated problems is a problem of young persons.

Determinants of alcohol use

Many factors have been identified as determinants of alcohol use. These include family history of alcohol use and genetics, gender, cultural practices, availability, accessibility and cost of purchase of alcohol [16-20]. It has long been observed that alcohol tends to run in families. This biological observation is further supported by genetic studies in which alcoholism in adoptees correlates more strongly with their biological parents than their adoptee parents [21-24]

The use of alcohol and its effects are more common in men than women, younger than older individuals, but the gap is narrowing due to changing patterns of alcohol consumption in many parts of the world [25]. In many cultures, it is more acceptable for men to drink alcohol than women, especially in the open. [26] This cultural practice makes for underreporting of alcohol use among women with far-reaching implications for, screening, prevention and treatment of alcohol use disorders. Also, it is common knowledge that society has subtly recommended particular alcoholic beverages or brands like wines, fruity alcoholic drinks, lower alcohol by volume beverages for women. Again, this creates an impression of lower use of alcohol in women than men. This is an area of developing research.

The availability of alcohol and cultural endorsement of the use of alcohol during ceremonies of birth, naming, marriages, burial and coronation also determines alcohol use largely. Studies show that individuals, exposed to alcohol use early in life with community endorsement, are more likely to continue alcohol use and develop problems compared to their counterparts, who do not have early alcohol exposure and community endorsement [27]. In fact, alcohol is considered a type of food in many African communities [11].

Traditionally, alcohol consumption reduces with increasing unit cost of a drink [28]. Nowadays, there are controversies about increasing alcohol consumption with increasing cost of alcoholic beverages [28]. Various reasons have been adduced to this phenomenon. The pleasure industry is usually unaffected during economic crises. People develop ingenious alternatives to get high and seek pleasure. The proliferation of countless brands of spirits in sachets and mini bottles, most of which cost less than 300 Naira per unit in the Nigerian Alcohol market is a case in point. The higher the inflation and economic crises, the higher problem

drinking [28], which is in agreement with “...the urge to escape, the longing to transcend themselves if only for a few moments, is and has always been the principal appetite of the soul”-Aldous Huxley [31]. Others have noted that increasing population growth, correlates with increasing alcohol consumption. Summarily, the factors that determine human behaviours, including alcohol use is not a linear relationship.

Studies show that younger persons use alcohol more than older persons [27]. Other studies show that there has been increasing drinking rates and pattern among older individuals, although with local and regional variations, as well as, changing patterns of consumption [28]. Similarly, males use more alcohol than females, but newer evidences [26] suggests that females, including pregnant women and nursing mothers, are drinking more than it was traditionally thought, probably due to a clandestine drinking pattern, availability of the preferred fruity and lower concentrations of alcoholic beverages, even in sachets, giving a misleading picture of lesser and safer use of alcohol compared to their male counterparts.

Materials and Methods

The study location was in Benue South Senatorial District with a total of nine LGAs. Four Hundred (400) participants between 18-60 years were recruited consecutively from three local governments of Okpokwu, Ohimini and Otukpo in the study. The three LGAs were chosen after three, consecutive, blind, random, selection without replacement from the nine LGAs. The sites where the questionnaires were administered were purposively and conveniently chosen. Ugbokolo market (Okpokwu), Otukpo main market (Otukpo) and a semi-urban community, Oglewu-Anmoda (Ohimini) were the sites of data collection. A 2-part sociodemographic questionnaire attached to the WHO widely validated ASSIST questionnaire was used for data collection. The sociodemographic questionnaire elicited information regarding age, sex, occupation, education level, religion, income, family type, parenting style, access to psychoactive substances, community control of psychoactive substances, ease of obtaining substances. Sample size determination was by the study conducted by Jatau et al [29].

The minimum sample size is calculated using the formula below:

$$n = \frac{NZ^2(1-P)}{d^2(N-1)+Z^2(1-p)} \quad (1)$$

Where;

n = sample size with infinite population correction

N = population size

Z = Z statistic for a level of confidence

P = Expected proportion and

d = precision.

N = 1,307,647 was used, which is the population of Benue South Senatorial District [30].

A minimum sample size of 368 was arrived at using the prevalence of 40% [29]

and 5% tolerable margin of error at 95% confidence interval. A 10% attrition rate was used which gave 37 participants giving a total of 400 participants recruited for the study.

Sampling technique

All 9 LGAs were written on separate sheets of paper and rolled up as small balls and placed in a cylinder and thoroughly mixed up. A research assistant then picked a ball at a time without replacement. The content of the cylinder was thoroughly mixed up again and another ball is picked without replacement. This was repeated for the third time and Okpokwu, Otukpo and Ohimini turned out to be the 3 LGAs that were randomly selected.

Questionnaire Administration and Data collection

A 3-part structured interviewer-administered questionnaire was administered to all eligible participants by trained research assistants that speak the local languages which is Idoma and Igede. The questionnaires collected information on sociodemographic characteristics and psychoactive substance use determinants. Sociodemographic information include age, sex, marital status, highest level of education, occupation, monthly income, psychoactive substance use determinants like community control of substances, ease of obtaining substances. The well validated WHO Alcohol, Smoking and Substance Involvement Screening Test (ASSIST) was the 3rd part of the questionnaire used to determine the prevalence of alcohol use. Statistical analysis was performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 (IBM Corp Released 2013). Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) was calculated for continuous variables while frequencies and proportions were generated for categorical variables. Chi-square test (χ^2) was used to test the association between variables for psychoactive substance use determinants.

Significance level of $p < 0.05$ was used and results were presented in tables.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval with protocol number: **FUHSO-HREC 02/05/2023** was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of the Federal University of Health Sciences, Otukpo (FUHSO), before commencement of the study. Each participant freely signed an informed consent form before participation. They were informed that they could opt out the study at any time and some did.

Results

Table: 1 Socio-Demographic Profile of the Participants: N = 400

Variables	Number of Participants	Percentage
Age		
18-25	194	48.5
26-33	87	21.7
34-60	119	29.8
mean age: 29.12 years ± 10.5		
Gender		
Male	287	70.4
Female	117	29.6
Marital status		
Single	243	60.7
Married	151	37.8
Widowed/widower	4	2.5
Educational level		
No formal	8	2.0
Primary	32	8.0
Secondary	236	59.0
Tertiary	118	29.5
Other	6	1.5
Occupation		
Artisans	100	25.0
Civil servants	14	3.5
Clergymen	16	4.0

Business	159	39.7
Farming	12	3.0
Students	66	16.5
Other	33	8.3
Ethnicity		
Idoma	291	72.8
Igede	14	3.5
Tiv	9	2.3
Igbo	48	12.0
Igala	13	3.3
Hausa	11	2.6
Other	14	3.5
Religion		
Christianity	371	92.8
Islam	29	7.2

Table: 2: Prevalence of Alcohol Use

Substance	Lifetime use	Use in the past 3 months
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Alcohol	310 (77.5)	190 (47.5)

Note: Use in the past 3 months represents current drinking.

Table 3: Prevalence of Graded Risk of Current Alcohol Use

Low risk	Moderate risk	High risk
80 (42.3 %)	90 (47.1%)	20 (10.6%)

Note: Current use represents use in the last 3 months.

Table 4: Association between Alcohol use and determinants

Categories	LRU		P-value	MRU		P-value	HRU		P-value
	Yes	No		Yes	No		Yes	No	
Gender			0.747			0.545			0.163
Male (n=182)	114(84.4)	68(86.1)		67(87.0)	115(83.9)		1(50.0)	181(85.4)	
Female (n=32)	21(15.15)	6(13.9)		10(13.0)	22(16.1)		1(50.0)	31(14.6)	
Age(years)			0.080			0.213			0.043
18-30 (n=140)	94(69.6)	46(58.2)		46(59.7)	94(68.6)		0(0.0)	140(66.0)	
31-45 (n=52)	26(19.3)	26(32.9)		24(31.2)	28(20.4)		2(100)	50(23.6)	
45-60 (n=22)	15(11.1)	7(8.9)		7(9.1)	15(10.9)		0(0.0)	22(10.4)	
Education Level			0.415			0.497			0.934
No formal education(n=3)	3(2.2)	0(0.0)		0(0.0)	3(2.2)		0(0.0)	3(1.4)	
Primary(n=20)	14(10.4)	6(7.6)		6(7.8)	14(10.2)		0(0.0)	20(9.4)	
Secondary(n=122)	73(54.1)	49(62.0)		47(61.0)	75(54.7)		1(50.0)	121(57.1)	
Tertiary(n=69)	45(33.3)	24(30.4)		24(31.2)	45(32.8)		1(50.0)	68(32.1)	
Ease of obtaining substances			0.453			0.407			0.920
Very easy(n=140)	90(66.7)	50(63.3)		48(63.6)	91(66.4)		1(50.0)	139(65.6)	
Easy(n=62)	40(29.6)	22(27.8)		21(27.3)	41(29.9)		1(50.0)	61(28.8)	

Difficult(n=9)	4(3.0) 5(6.3)		5(6.5) 4(2.9)		0(0.0) 9(4.2)	
Very difficult(n=3)	1(0.7) 20(2.5)		2(2.6) 1(0.8)		0(0.0) 3(1.4)	
Effectiveness of substance control		0.112		0.080		0.451
Yes(n=47)	25(18.5) 22(27.8)		22(28.6) 25(18.2)		0(0.0) 47(22.2)	
No(n=167)	110(81.5)57(72.2)		55(71.4)112(81.8)		2(100)165(77.8)	
LRU=Low risk use	MRU=Moderate risk use		*HRU=High risk use			

Of the 400 participants, 48.5 % were in the age bracket of 18-25 years, while 21.7% were between 26-33 years. Majority (70.4%) are males, while females constitute 29.6%. Singles were 60.7%, while those that were married were 37.8%. Those that had secondary school education were 59%, while 2% had no formal education. Nearly forty (39.7%) per cent were doing business, while those that were farming were 3%. Idomas were 72.8%, while Tivs constituted 2.3%. Christians were 92.8%, while Moslems were 7.2% see table 1.

The lifetime prevalence of alcohol use was 77.5%, while prevalence for current alcohol use was 47.5% see table 2.

Table 3 shows the prevalence of graded risk for current alcohol use. 42.3% were low risk users, while 47.1% and 10.6% were moderate and high-risk users respectively. Table 4 shows that there was no association between gender and all three risk levels of alcohol use (P=0.747, 0.545, and 0.163). Also, age, educational level, ease of obtaining psychoactive substances and effectiveness of control of psychoactive substances shows no association with all three risk levels of alcohol use see table 4.

Discussion

The lifetime and current prevalence of alcohol use in this study were 77.5% and 47.5% respectively. This was highest among the 18–25-year-old participants, male, who are middle born with secondary school education. The mean age of the participants was 29.12 years ± 10.5 years.

The current use prevalence of 47.5% in this study is higher than a prevalence of 23.7% reported by Lasebikan and Ola in South West Nigeria [13]. Although Lasebikan and Ola used the ASSIST Instrument in their study, they did not use the standard scoring instructions in scoring their prevalence. Also, they had a larger sample size of 1,203 compared to 400 participants in our study. They combined prevalence of moderate and high-risk use in their study. All of these could account for the difference in their prevalence and ours.

Onodugbo and his colleagues in South East, Nigeria [14] reported a prevalence of 66.7% which is higher than our study finding. This could be due to a larger sample size

of 1411 in their study compared to 400 in our study. Also, the instruments for data collection for alcohol were different for both studies. Adeloje and his colleagues got a crude prevalence of 34.3% [15], which is lower than our finding. This could be due to the design of systematic review and meta-analysis of 35 pooled studies compared to a single cross-sectional design of our study. The finding of a high prevalence of current alcohol use in our study is in keeping with the socio-cultural disposition of alcohol in many African societies, where alcohol is part and parcel of the daily lives of the people and it is even considered a type of food [10,11].

Of the 47.5% current drinkers, 10.6% are high risk users. This proportion are likely to be dependent drinkers and have more problems with their drinking pattern. They will require further assessment and more than brief interventions.

This study found no association between alcohol use and gender (p=0.163), age (p=0.043), educational level (p=0.934), community control of alcohol use (p=0.451) and ease of obtaining alcohol (p=0.920). This is contrary to the findings in many studies that have found associations between alcohol use and several determinants [10,11,13,14,15,18]. This could be due to the emerging global trend of changing and unpredictable alcohol drinking pattern across cultures and over time [26,27,28].

Conclusion

The prevalence of alcohol use in Benue South Senatorial District, Nigeria is high and consistent with findings from other studies. This calls for more research on alcohol use alongside routine screening and intervention in health facilities.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to thank all the participants who consented and took part in this study.

We also thank the management of FUHSO, TETFUND and community leaders and gate keepers for providing the enabling environment and support for this research effort.

We acknowledge the efforts of the field workers who collected the data.

Financial sponsorship

This research effort is wholly sponsored financially by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) of Nigeria as part of the 2022 Institution Based Research (IBR) for Nigerian Universities.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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